

PERMANENTS OF 3×3 INVERTIBLE MATRICES MODULO N

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Abstract

Let $GL_3(\mathbb{Z}_n)$ denote the set of 3×3 invertible matrices with entries from \mathbb{Z}_n , the ring of integers modulo n . We study the distribution of a matrix function called the permanent, restricting its domain to $GL_3(\mathbb{Z}_n)$. Given $x \in \mathbb{Z}$, we count the number of elements in the set $G_3(n, x) = \{M \in GL_3(\mathbb{Z}_n) \mid \text{perm}(M) \equiv x \pmod{n}\}$.

1. Introduction

The aim of this paper is to carry forward the work done in [1] for 2×2 matrices to 3×3 matrices. We begin by recalling some definitions and notation. Let $GL_r(\mathbb{Z}_n)$ denote the set of $r \times r$ invertible matrices with entries from \mathbb{Z}_n , the ring of integers modulo n . Let S_n denote the group of permutations on n symbols. The *permanent* of an $n \times n$ matrix $A = [a_{ij}]$ is defined as

$$\text{perm}(A) = \sum_{\sigma \in S_n} \prod_{i=1}^n a_{i\sigma(i)}.$$

In [1], we determined the number of invertible 2×2 matrices modulo n having a given permanent x (see the function $g_n(x)$ in [1]). The *permanent* function looks similar to the *determinant*, which is defined as

$$\det(A) = \sum_{\sigma \in S_n} \prod_{i=1}^n \text{sgn}(\sigma) a_{i\sigma(i)}.$$

The determinant represents a geometric idea as well as an algebraic one. Geometrically, it is the volume (with orientation) of the parallelepiped formed by the rows

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(or columns). Algebraically, it is the product of the eigenvalues, counted with multiplicity. Although the permanent too plays an important role in graph theory (see [7],[5],[6],[9]) but it does not seem to have a geometric/algebraic interpretation.

It is well-known that the determinant can be computed in polynomial time. In particular, by applying the Gauss Elimination method one can show its complexity of computation is $\sim O(n^3)$. But there is no efficient algorithm known which can compute the permanent in polynomial time and it is unlikely that it even exists. The most-well known algorithm for computing the permanent is Ryser’s Algorithm [2] which has an asymptotic complexity $O(n2^n)$. Even for matrices with entries from the set $\{0, 1\}$, Valiant shows in [8] that the computation of the permanent of such matrices is a P-complete problem.

In view of this, the natural way to proceed has been to ask if one can use the determinant to compute the permanent. Given a commutative ring R with unity, does there exist a transformation $\Phi : M_n(R) \rightarrow M_m(R)$ such that $perm(A) = det(\Phi(A))$? An insightful discussion of the existence of such transformations of matrices over finite fields and their characteristics can be found in [4]. A new method for obtaining lower bounds on the number of matrices over a finite field with nonzero permanent is developed in [3].

The route we take in this paper is not based on the complexities of computation of the permanent. Rather, we discuss the distribution of the permanent values modulo n and count exactly the number of matrices having a given permanent modulo n . In doing this, we highlight the role that the prime divisors of n play. We introduce our main object of study now.

Let

$$G_3(n, x) = \{M \in GL_3(\mathbb{Z}_n) \mid perm(M) \equiv x \pmod{n}\}.$$

Let $g_3(n, x)$ denote the cardinality of $G_3(n, x)$. We recall some results from the discussion of the 2×2 case (see [1]) which carry over naturally to 3×3 matrices as well.

1. **Multiplicative Property (MP):** For $a, b, x \in \mathbb{N}$, $(a, b) = 1$, we have $g_3(ab, x) = g_3(a, x) \times g_3(b, x)$.
2. **Invariance Property (IP):** Let p be a prime number and $k \in \mathbb{N}$. Let $m \in \mathbb{N}$ be such that $p \nmid m$. Then for $1 \leq r \leq k$ we have $g_3(p^k, p^r) = g_3(p^k, mp^r)$. We also have $g(p^k, 1) = g(p^k, u)$ whenever $p \nmid u$. This property actually partitions $GL_3(\mathbb{Z}_{p^k})$ in the following manner:

$$|GL_3(\mathbb{Z}_{p^k})| = \sum_{i=0}^k \varphi(p^i) \times g_3(p^k, p^{k-i}).$$

Since in this paper, we are dealing primarily with 3×3 matrices, from now on we will simply write $g(n, x)$ to denote $g_3(n, x)$. When we will talk specifically about 2×2 matrices, we will use the notation $g_2(n, x)$.

We now elaborate on the organization of the paper. Our main goal in this paper is to compute $g(n, x)$. Since this function is multiplicative in n , it is sufficient to know $g(p^k, x)$, where p is a prime number and $k \in \mathbb{N}$. Therefore the main result we will establish is the following.

Theorem 1. *Let p be a prime. Let $k, x \in \mathbb{N}$. Then*

$$g(p^k, x) = \begin{cases} p^{8(k-1)}g(p, 0) & \text{if } p \mid x, \\ p^{8(k-1)} \frac{|GL_3(\mathbb{Z}_p)| - g(p, 0)}{p-1} & \text{otherwise.} \end{cases}$$

These values look arbitrary at first, but they are an extension of the analogous result in [1].

Theorem 2. *Let p be a prime. Let $k, x \in \mathbb{N}$. Then $g(p^k, x)$ assumes only two distinct values. Specifically,*

$$g(p^k, x) = \begin{cases} g(p^k, 0) & \text{if } p \mid x, \\ g(p^k, 1) & \text{otherwise.} \end{cases}$$

This looks similar to the IP but it tells us much more. For example, from IP we cannot get $g(p^4, p) = g(p^4, 2p^2)$, where p is an odd prime number but one can by using Theorem 2. Furthermore, knowing $g(p^k, 0)$ is sufficient to determine $g(p^k, 1)$. Since for all $i, 1 \leq i \leq k$ we have $g(p^k, 0) = g(p^k, p^i)$, and the telescoping sum:

$$\begin{aligned} |GL_3(\mathbb{Z}_{p^k})| &= g(p^k, 0) + \sum_{i=1}^{k-1} (p^i - p^{i-1}) \times g(p^k, 0) + \varphi(p^k) \times g(p^k, 1) \\ &= p^{k-1} \times g(p^k, 0) + (p^k - p^{k-1}) \times g(p^k, 1). \end{aligned}$$

Since $|GL_3(\mathbb{Z}_{p^k})| = p^{9(k-1)}|GL_3(\mathbb{Z}_p)| = p^{9(k-1)}(p^3 - 1)(p^3 - p)(p^3 - p^2)$, once we know $g(p^k, 0)$ we can also evaluate $g(p^k, 1)$. Thus, the paper boils down to computing $g(p, 0)$. It is clear that $g(2, 0) = 0$. The following result will be proved in the last section 4.

Theorem 3. *Let p be an odd prime. Then*

$$g(p, 0) = \begin{cases} p(p-1)^4[(p+1)^3 + 1] & \text{if } (p-3) \text{ is a quadratic residue modulo } p, \\ p^2(p-1)^4(p^2 + 3p + 5) & \text{otherwise.} \end{cases}$$

We dedicate Section 2 to the proof of Theorem 2. In Section 3 we derive the proof of Theorem 1 using Theorem 2. In Section 4 we prove Theorem 3 in two different ways.

2. The Range of $g(p^k, x)$

In this section we prove Theorem 2. We will start by showing that $g(p^k, 0) = g(p^k, p^r)$ whenever $1 \leq r \leq k$. That coupled with IP will prove Theorem 2. For this section, we introduce some notation. Given a 3×3 matrix A , let $P_{ij}(A)$ be the permanent of 2×2 submatrix obtained by deleting row i and column j of A . Given a prime $p, k, x \in \mathbb{N}, 1 \leq i, j \leq 3$, define the following sets:

- $G(p^k, x, 1, 1) = \{A \in G(p^k, x) : p \nmid P_{11}(A)\},$
- $G(p^k, x, 1, 2) = \{A \in G(p^k, x) : p \mid P_{11}(A), p \nmid P_{12}(A)\},$
- $G(p^k, x, 1, 3) = \{A \in G(p^k, x) : p \mid P_{11}(A), P_{12}(A), p \nmid P_{13}(A)\},$
- $G(p^k, x, 2, 1) = \{A \in G(p^k, x) : p \mid P_{11}(A), P_{12}(A), P_{13}(A), p \nmid P_{21}(A)\},$
- $G(p^k, x, 2, 2) = \{A \in G(p^k, x) : p \mid P_{11}(A), P_{12}(A), P_{13}(A), P_{21}(A), p \nmid P_{22}(A)\}.$

In a similar way, one can define the sets $G(p^k, x, 2, 3), G(p^k, x, 3, 1), G(p^k, x, 3, 2)$ and $G(p^k, x, 3, 3)$. An interesting observation is that for an odd prime p such that $p \mid x$, the sets

$$G(p^k, x, 1, 1), G(p^k, x, 1, 2), G(p^k, x, 1, 3), G(p^k, x, 2, 1) \text{ and } G(p^k, x, 2, 2)$$

are always non-empty, containing the matrices

$$\begin{pmatrix} \frac{x-1}{2} & \frac{x+1}{2} & 0 \\ 1 & 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 \end{pmatrix}, \begin{pmatrix} 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 1 & 1 & 1 \\ 0 & 1 & x-1 \end{pmatrix}, \begin{pmatrix} 1 & 0 & 0 \\ (x-1)^{-1} & 1 & 1 \\ x-1 & 1 & x-1 \end{pmatrix},$$

$$\begin{pmatrix} 0 & 0 & 1 \\ 1 & 1 & 0 \\ x-1 & 1 & 0 \end{pmatrix} \text{ and } \begin{pmatrix} 1 & 1 & 1 \\ 0 & 1 & 1 \\ 0 & 1 & x-1 \end{pmatrix},$$

respectively. Can we assure the non-emptiness of the remaining four sets, namely

$$G(p^k, x, 2, 3), G(p^k, x, 3, 1), G(p^k, x, 3, 2) \text{ and } G(p^k, x, 3, 3)?$$

The following lemma shows that it is not possible, no matter what the constraints on x are.

Lemma 1. *Let p be a prime number. Let $k, x \in \mathbb{N}$. Then the sets*

$$G(p^k, x, 2, 3), G(p^k, x, 3, 1), G(p^k, x, 3, 2) \text{ and } G(p^k, x, 3, 3)$$

are empty sets.

Proof. We will show that if $A = [a_{ij}]$ with p dividing $P_{11}(A), P_{12}(A), P_{13}(A), P_{21}(A)$ and $P_{22}(A)$ then A will fail to be invertible. It is easy to verify the following identity:

$$2a_{22}P_{22}(A) - a_{11}P_{11}(A) + a_{12}P_{12}(A) - 2a_{21}P_{21}(A) - 3a_{13}P_{13}(A) = \det(A) - 6a_{13}a_{21}a_{32}.$$

At this stage, the lemma is already proved for $p = 2$ and $p = 3$. We give the proof for the remaining primes. Suppose that p had divided any one of a_{13}, a_{21} or a_{32} . Then we would be done.

We again assume the contrary. Suppose a_{13}^{-1}, a_{21}^{-1} and a_{32}^{-1} exist. Since

$$p \mid P_{11}(A), \text{ where } P_{11}(A) = a_{22}a_{33} + a_{23}a_{32}, \quad a_{23} \equiv -a_{22}a_{33}a_{32}^{-1} \pmod{p}.$$

We substitute this into $P_{12}(A) = a_{21}a_{33} + a_{23}a_{31} \equiv 0 \pmod{p}$, and we get $a_{33}(a_{21}a_{32} - a_{22}a_{31}) \equiv 0 \pmod{p}$. Suppose $p \mid a_{33}$. Then from $p \mid P_{11}(A)$, we see that $p \mid a_{23}$ and from $p \mid P_{21}(A)$, we get $p \mid a_{13}$, which is absurd. Thus, the only option is that $p \mid (a_{21}a_{32} - a_{22}a_{31})$. With a similar argument we can show that $p \mid a_{31}(a_{23}a_{32} - a_{22}a_{33})$. Finally we are left with

$$p \mid (a_{21}a_{32} - a_{22}a_{31}) \text{ and } p \mid (a_{22}a_{33} - a_{23}a_{32}).$$

Multiplying the first equation by a_{33} and the second by a_{31} and subtracting, we arrive at $p \mid a_{32}(a_{21}a_{33} - a_{23}a_{31})$. Since $p \nmid a_{32}$, we have $p \mid (a_{21}a_{33} - a_{23}a_{31})$ and hence $p \mid \det(A)$, a contradiction. \square

Theorem 5 in Section 4 provides exact values of $g(p, 0, i, j) = |G(p, 0, i, j)|$.

Lemma 2. *Let p be a prime number. Let $k, x \in \mathbb{N}$ be such that $p \mid x$. Then $g(p^k, 0) = g(p^k, x)$.*

Proof. Instead of giving a single bijection from $G(p^k, 0)$ to $G(p^k, x)$ we will give a bijection from $G(p^k, 0, i, j)$ to $G(p^k, x, i, j)$. Since we will do this for all i, j $1 \leq i, j \leq 3$, we would have in effect shown $g(p^k, 0) = g(p^k, x)$ whenever $p \mid x$.

After Lemma 1, we only need to prove the above for

$$G(p^k, x, 1, 1), G(p^k, x, 1, 2), G(p^k, x, 1, 3), G(p^k, x, 2, 1) \text{ and } G(p^k, x, 2, 2).$$

We prove it for $G(p^k, 0, 1, 1)$. The remaining four can then be proved similarly. Define the map:

$$\psi_{11} : G(p^k, 0, 1, 1) \rightarrow G(p^k, x, 1, 1) \text{ by } \begin{pmatrix} a_{11} & a_{12} & a_{13} \\ a_{21} & a_{22} & a_{23} \\ a_{31} & a_{32} & a_{33} \end{pmatrix} \mapsto \begin{pmatrix} a_{11} + \frac{x}{P_{11}} & a_{12} & a_{13} \\ a_{21} & a_{22} & a_{23} \\ a_{31} & a_{32} & a_{33} \end{pmatrix}.$$

The important thing to see here is that the map ψ_{11} preserves invertibility since we are translating the determinant by a multiple of p . This would not be guaranteed

if we had done a similar operation from $G(p^k, 1, 1, 1)$ to $G(p^k, x, 1, 1)$, $p \mid x$. Now it is easy to check that ψ_{11} is an injective map. For surjectivity, if

$$M = \begin{pmatrix} b_{11} & b_{12} & b_{13} \\ b_{21} & b_{22} & b_{23} \\ b_{31} & b_{32} & b_{33} \end{pmatrix} \in G(p^k, x, 1, 1),$$

then $\psi_{11}(N) = M$, where

$$N = \begin{pmatrix} b_{11} - \frac{x}{p_{11}} & b_{12} & b_{13} \\ b_{21} & b_{22} & b_{23} \\ b_{31} & b_{32} & b_{33} \end{pmatrix} \in G(p^k, 0, 1, 1).$$

Consequently, the map ψ_{11} is a bijection. Hence, we see that $|G(p^k, 0, 1, 1)| = |G(p^k, x, 1, 1)|$. Similarly, we can show

$$|G(p^k, 0, 1, 2)| = |G(p^k, x, 1, 2)|, |G(p^k, 0, 1, 3)| = |G(p^k, x, 1, 3)|,$$

$$|G(p^k, 0, 2, 1)| = |G(p^k, x, 2, 1)| \text{ and } |G(p^k, 0, 2, 2)| = |G(p^k, x, 2, 2)|.$$

But since their disjoint unions are exactly $G(p^k, 0)$ and $G(p^k, x)$ respectively, thus we have $g(p^k, 0) = g(p^k, x)$, whenever $p \mid x$. \square

Now the proof of Theorem 2 can be obtained from IP which gives $g(p^k, 1) = g(p^k, y)$ when $p \nmid y$ and Lemma 2 which gives $g(p^k, 0) = g(p^k, x)$ when $p \mid x$.

3. Computing $g(p^k, x)$

In this section, our goal is to prove Theorem 1. In particular, from Theorem 2 it is sufficient to find $g(p^k, 0)$ and $g(p^k, 1)$ and furthermore, with our earlier discussion, it reduces to finding $g(p^k, 0)$. For a given odd prime p and $k \in \mathbb{N}$, we define the set $G_{p^k} = \bigcup_{p \mid x} G(p^k, x)$. We have $|G_{p^k}| = p^{k-1}g(p^k, 0)$, since

$$|\{x \mid 1 \leq x \leq n, p \mid x\}| = p^k - \varphi(p^k) = p^{k-1}.$$

We define the map $\pi_{p^k} : G_{p^k} \rightarrow G(p, 0)$ as $[c_{ij}] \mapsto [c_{ij} \pmod{p}]$. It is easy to see that if $A = [a_{ij}] \in G(p, 0)$, then $|\pi_{p^k}^{-1}(A)| = p^{9(k-1)}$ as if $B = [b_{ij}] \in \pi_{p^k}^{-1}(A)$, then $b_{ij} = a_{ij} + c_{ij}$, where $p \mid c_{ij}$. The following example illustrates the same.

Example 4. Consider the case when $p = 3$ and $k = 2$. Then, the set G_9 will be:

$$G_9 = G(9, 0) \cup G(9, 3) \cup G(9, 6).$$

Condition	Subconditions	Number of matrices
Only one entry in the 1st row is nonzero		$3p^2(p-1)^4$
Only one entry in 1st row is zero	Only one entry in 2nd row is nonzero Only one entry in 2nd row is zero All the entries of 2nd row are nonzero	$3p(p-1)^4$ $6p(p-1)^5 + 3p^2(p-1)^4$ $3p(p-1)^6$
All the entries of 1st row are nonzero	Only one entry in 2nd row is nonzero Only one entry in 2nd row is zero All the entries of 2nd row are nonzero	$3p(p-1)^5$ $3p(p-1)^6$ **
Here ** = $\begin{cases} p^2(p-1)^5(p-2) & \text{if } p-3 \text{ is not a quadratic residue modulo } p, \\ p(p-1)^5(p^2-2p-2) & \text{if } p-3 \text{ is a quadratic residue modulo } p. \end{cases}$		

Table 1: Computation of $g(p, 0)$.

The map π_9 reduces every matrix in G to a matrix in $G(3, 0)$. Furthermore, each element of $G(3, 0)$ has $3^9 = 19683$ preimages. For example consider the matrix $\begin{pmatrix} 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 2 & 1 & 2 \\ 1 & 1 & 1 \end{pmatrix} \in G(3, 0)$. It has a preimage $\begin{pmatrix} 4 & 0 & 0 \\ 2 & 1 & 2 \\ 1 & 1 & 1 \end{pmatrix} \in G(9, 3)$. The matrix $\begin{pmatrix} 1 & 3 & 0 \\ 2 & 1 & 2 \\ 1 & 1 & 1 \end{pmatrix} \in G(9, 6)$ is also an example of a preimage.

Now the proof of Theorem 1 follows from the following equation which was derived from the discussion before the previous example.

$$\begin{aligned} p^{k-1}g(p^k, 0) &= p^{9(k-1)}g(p, 0), \\ g(p^k, 0) &= p^{8(k-1)}g(p, 0). \end{aligned}$$

Now we can also get the exact value of $g(p^k, 1)$ in the following manner.

$$\begin{aligned} |GL_3(\mathbb{Z}_{p^k})| &= p^{9(k-1)} \times |GL_3(\mathbb{Z}_p)| \\ &= p^{(k-1)} \times g(p^k, 0) + (p^k - p^{(k-1)}) \times g(p^k, 1). \\ g(p^k, 1) &= p^{8(k-1)} \frac{|GL_3(\mathbb{Z}_p)| - g(p, 0)}{p-1}. \end{aligned}$$

4. Computation of $g(p, 0)$

Table 1 summarizes how we compute $g(p, 0)$. We illustrate a few cases, the procedure for the remaining cases is similar.

4.1. When the First Row Contains Only One Nonzero Entry

Without loss of generality, let $A = [a_{ij}]$ with $a_{11} \neq 0, a_{12} = a_{13} = 0$. Clearly, a_{11} has a total of $(p - 1)$ choices. We now look at the possible choices for the other six entries of A . Consider the submatrix $\begin{pmatrix} a_{22} & a_{23} \\ a_{32} & a_{33} \end{pmatrix}$. The permanent of this matrix has to be divisible by p and determinant cannot be divisible by p . From [1], there are a total of $g_2(p, 0) = (p - 1)^3$ choices for the four entries a_{22}, a_{23}, a_{32} and a_{33} . The remaining two entries a_{21} and a_{31} each have p choices. So the total number of ways becomes $p^2 \times (p - 1)^4$. Hence the total choices in this case is $3p^2 \times (p - 1)^4$.

4.2. Exactly Two Entries in the First Row are Nonzero and All the Entries in the Second Row Are Nonzero

Let

$$A = \begin{pmatrix} a_{11} & a_{12} & 0 \\ a_{21} & a_{22} & a_{23} \\ x & y & z \end{pmatrix} \in G(p, 0).$$

Then each entry in the second row has $(p - 1)$ choices. The congruences for A are now

$$\begin{aligned} perm(A) &= a_{11}(a_{22}z + a_{33}y) + a_{12}(a_{21}z + a_{23}x) \equiv 0 \pmod{p}, \\ det(A) &= a_{11}(a_{22}z - a_{33}y) - a_{12}(a_{21}z - a_{23}x) \not\equiv 0 \pmod{p}. \end{aligned}$$

Let z be the free variable, so it has p choices. Now we will exclude certain values of x and y which will fail invertibility of A . We do not want the following system to have a solution, after we fix $z = z_o$:

$$\begin{aligned} a_{12}a_{23}x + a_{11}a_{23}y &\equiv -z_o(a_{11}a_{22} + a_{12}a_{21}), \\ a_{12}a_{23}x - a_{11}a_{23}y &\equiv -z_o(a_{11}a_{22} - a_{12}a_{21}). \end{aligned}$$

Since the determinant of the coefficient matrix is invertible, this system admits a unique solution, which will make A non-invertible. So we exclude that one choice of (x, y) . Now choosing any of the $(p - 1)$ values of x and using the permanent congruence to get a uniquely determined value of y will work. Thus, there are a total of $(p - 1)$ ways to choose the ordered pair (x, y) . After considering choices for the first row we end up with $3p(p - 1)^6$ ways.

4.3. If All the Entries of the First Row Are Nonzero and Only One Entry in the Second Row Is Nonzero

In this situation the matrix looks like

$$A = \begin{pmatrix} a & b & c \\ \alpha & \beta & \gamma \\ x & y & z \end{pmatrix} \in G(p, 0),$$

where only one of α, β, γ is nonzero. Suppose $\alpha \neq 0, \beta = \gamma = 0$. There are $(p - 1)$ choices for α . The congruences for A are now:

$$\begin{aligned} \text{perm}(A) &= \alpha(cy + bz) \equiv 0 \pmod{p}, \\ \det(A) &= \alpha(cy - bz) \not\equiv 0 \pmod{p}. \end{aligned}$$

Since x does not appear in the above equations, it is free and has p choices. We need to exclude one choice for (y, z) , namely, the unique solution to this system:

$$\begin{aligned} \alpha(cy + bz) &\equiv 0 \pmod{p}, \\ \alpha(cy - bz) &\equiv 0 \pmod{p}. \end{aligned}$$

After throwing that choice of (y, z) , we are left with $(p - 1)$ choices for the ordered pair (y, z) . Thus the total ways in this subcase after including the choices for the first row is $3p(p - 1)^5$. The factor 3 appears because we could have started with $\beta \neq 0$ or $\gamma \neq 0$.

Adding up all the possibilities, we arrive at:

$$\begin{aligned} g(p, 0) &= 3p^2(p - 1)^4 + 3p^2(p - 1)^4(p + 1) + (p - 1)^3[3p(p - 1)^2 + 3p(p - 1)^3 \\ &\qquad\qquad\qquad + p^2(p - 1)^2(p - 2)] \\ &= 3p^2(p - 1)^4 + 3p^2(p - 1)^4(p + 1) + p(p - 1)^5[3 + 3p - 3 + p^2 - 2p] \\ &= 3p^2(p - 1)^4 + 3p^2(p - 1)^4(p + 1) + p^2(p - 1)^5(p + 1) \\ &= p^2(p - 1)^4(p^2 + 3p + 5). \end{aligned}$$

Let us check this with the actual value which a computer code gives out.

1. When $p = 3, g(3, 0) = 9 \times 16 \times 23 = 3312$
2. When $p = 5, g(5, 0) = 25 \times 256 \times 45 = 288000$
3. When $p = 7, g(7, 0) = 49 \times 36 \times 36 \times 75 = 4762800$
4. When $p = 11, g(11, 0) = 121 \times 10000 \times 159 = 192390000$.
5. When $p = 13, g(13, 0) = 169 \times 144 \times 144 \times 213 = 746433792$.

The computer program agrees with our values when $p = 3, 5, 11$ but not when $p = 7, 13$. The code gives an output of $g(7, 0) = 4653936$ and $g(13, 0) = 739964160$. So what is different in these cases? Let us consider the case when $p = 7$ and the

following matrix $A = \begin{pmatrix} 1 & 1 & 2 \\ 1 & 2 & 1 \\ x & y & z \end{pmatrix}$. The equations for this matrix become

$$\begin{aligned} \text{perm}(A) &= 5x + 3y + 3z \equiv 0 \pmod{7}, \\ \det(A) &= 4x + y + z \not\equiv 0 \pmod{7}. \end{aligned}$$

After a quick inspection, one can see that there is no ordered triad (x, y, z) satisfying the above two congruences as $5(5x + 3y + 3z) \equiv 4x + y + z \pmod{7}$. But when we take the same matrix but change p to 3, 5 or 11 then the system admits a solution. So there is something different with the prime 7 here and 13 too, because they are throwing out some additional choices for the second row as well, apart from the multiples of the first row.

4.4. Role of Quadratic Residues

We noticed that when $n = 7$, each determinant of the three 2×2 submatrices formed from last two rows was a nonzero scalar multiple of the respective permanents of those submatrices. Let us explore this further. Note that we are in the case that

$p \nmid a \cdot b \cdot c \cdot \alpha \cdot \beta \cdot \gamma$, where $A = \begin{pmatrix} a & b & c \\ \alpha & \beta & \gamma \\ x & y & z \end{pmatrix} \in G(p, 0)$. Since $\gamma \neq 0$, it has $p - 1$ choices. Suppose that

$$\frac{b\gamma + c\beta}{b\gamma - c\beta} = \frac{c\alpha + a\gamma}{c\alpha - a\gamma} = \frac{a\beta + b\alpha}{a\beta - b\alpha} = \theta. \tag{1}$$

It is clear that $\frac{b\gamma + c\beta}{b\gamma - c\beta} \notin \{1, p - 1\}$ if for example, $\frac{b\gamma + c\beta}{b\gamma - c\beta} = 1$, then $c\beta = 0$. Thus $\theta \in \{2, 3, \dots, p - 2\}$. Also from Equation 1 we have the following,

$$\alpha = \frac{a\gamma(\theta + 1)}{c(\theta - 1)} = \frac{a\beta(\theta - 1)}{b(\theta + 1)}.$$

Again, from $\theta = \frac{b\gamma + c\beta}{b\gamma - c\beta}$ we have $\theta + 1 = \frac{2b\gamma}{b\gamma - c\beta}$ and $\theta - 1 = \frac{2c\beta}{b\gamma - c\beta}$. Substituting these values, we arrive at $\beta^3 = \frac{b^3\gamma^3}{c^3} = \left(\frac{b\gamma}{c}\right)^3$. Now from $b\gamma - c\beta \not\equiv 0 \pmod{p}$ we have,

$$\begin{aligned} \beta^3 - \left(\frac{b\gamma}{c}\right)^3 &\equiv \left(\beta - \frac{b\gamma}{c}\right) \left(\beta^2 + \left(\frac{b\gamma}{c}\right)\beta + \left(\frac{b\gamma}{c}\right)^2\right) \equiv 0 \pmod{p} \\ \text{implies } \beta^2 + \left(\frac{b\gamma}{c}\right)\beta + \left(\frac{b\gamma}{c}\right)^2 &\equiv 0 \pmod{p}. \end{aligned}$$

This means that β must solve the above quadratic congruence. That can only happen when, the following quadratic congruence in u admits a solution

$$u^2 \equiv \left(\frac{b\gamma}{c}\right)^2 - 4\left(\frac{b\gamma}{c}\right)^2 \equiv -3\left(\frac{b\gamma}{c}\right)^2 \pmod{p}.$$

According to Euler’s Criterion, the above quadratic congruence in u admits a solution if and only if

$$\left(-3\left(\frac{b\gamma}{c}\right)^2\right)^{\frac{p-1}{2}} \equiv (p-3)^{\frac{p-1}{2}} \equiv 1 \pmod{p}.$$

The above congruence is equivalent to the fact that $(p-3)$ is a quadratic residue modulo p . When $(p-3)$ is a quadratic residue modulo p , then for every choice of γ there will be two values of β which will each lead to a unique value of α for which we will not get any (x, y, z) satisfying the two congruences. Thus, the correction is merely $2(p-1)$. The expression now is $p(p-1)[(p-1)^3 - (p-1) - 2(p-1)] = p(p-1)^2[p^2 + 1 - 2p - 1 - 2] = p(p-1)^2(p^2 - 2p - 2)$. Thus, we arrive at the modified expression when $(p-3)$ is a quadratic residue modulo p as

$$g(p, 0) = p(p-1)^4[(p+1)^3 + 1].$$

A quick check gives us

- $g(7, 0) = 7 \times 36 \times 36 \times 513 = 4653936$,
- $g(13, 0) = 13 \times 144 \times 144 \times 2745 = 739964160$.

Both these values agree with the output given by the computer program. Theorem 3 is now proved.

4.5. Computation of $g(p, 0, i, j)$

If $p \mid x$, then one can observe more facts about the number of elements in the sets

$$G(p, x, 1, 1), G(p, x, 1, 2), G(p, x, 1, 3), G(p, x, 2, 1) \text{ and } G(p, x, 2, 2).$$

These observations can be derived from Table 2, which we now cement as a result.

Theorem 5. *Let p be an odd prime. Then*

1. $g(p, 0, 2, 2) = p(p-1)^4$,
2. $g(p, 0, 2, 1) = (3p-1)g(p, 0, 2, 2)$,
3. $g(p, 0, 1, 3) = (p-1)g(p, 0, 2, 2)$,
4. $g(p, 0, 1, 2) = p(p+1)g(p, 0, 2, 2)$,

n	g(n,0)	g(n,0,1,1)	g(n,0,1,2)	g(n,0,1,3)	g(n,0,2,1)	g(n,0,2,2)
3	3312	2208	576	96	384	48
5	288000	225280	38400	5120	17920	1280
7	4653936	3900960	508032	54432	181440	9072
9	21730032	14486688	3779136	629856	2519424	314928
11	192390000	173140000	14520000	1100000	3520000	110000
13	739964160	677154816	49061376	3234816	10243584	269568

Table 2: Some values of $g(n, 0, i, j)$.

$$5. \ g(p, 0, 1, 1) = \begin{cases} (p + 3)(p^2 - p + 1)g(p, 0, 2, 2) & \text{if } (p - 3)^{\frac{p-1}{2}} \equiv 1 \pmod{p}, \\ (p^3 + 2p^2 + 1)g(p, 0, 2, 2) & \text{otherwise.} \end{cases}$$

Proof. Let $A = \begin{pmatrix} a_{11} & a_{12} & a_{13} \\ a_{21} & a_{22} & a_{23} \\ a_{31} & a_{32} & a_{33} \end{pmatrix}$. Recall the following definitions.

$$P_{11}(A) = a_{22}a_{33} + a_{23}a_{32}, \quad P_{12}(A) = a_{21}a_{33} + a_{23}a_{31}, \quad P_{13}(A) = a_{21}a_{32} + a_{22}a_{31},$$

$$P_{21}(A) = a_{12}a_{33} + a_{13}a_{32}, \quad P_{22}(A) = a_{11}a_{33} + a_{13}a_{31}.$$

Note that in the rest of the proof, by $x = 0$ we mean $x \equiv 0 \pmod{p}$.

Proof of Part 1. First we show that $a_{22}a_{33} - a_{23}a_{32} \not\equiv 0 \pmod{p}$. For if it was, that would mean $a_{22}a_{33} \equiv 0 \pmod{p}$ and $a_{23}a_{32} \equiv 0 \pmod{p}$, as $p \mid P_{11}(A)$. So we are left with either of the four cases $(a_{22}, a_{23}) = (0, 0)$ or $(a_{22}, a_{32}) = (0, 0)$ or $(a_{33}, a_{23}) = (0, 0)$ or $(a_{33}, a_{32}) = (0, 0)$. Suppose $(a_{22}, a_{23}) = (0, 0)$. Then from $p \mid P_{12}(A)$, we have $a_{33} = 0$. Again from $p \mid P_{21}(A)$ we have $a_{13} = 0$ or $a_{32} = 0$. Both these choices contradict invertibility of A . The other three cases can be shown similarly. Thus, $a_{22}a_{33} - a_{23}a_{32} \not\equiv 0 \pmod{p}$. Since

$$a_{21}a_{33} + a_{23}a_{31} \equiv 0 \pmod{p}, \quad a_{21}a_{32} + a_{22}a_{31} \equiv 0 \pmod{p},$$

we are left with $a_{21} = a_{31} = 0$. Now $\begin{pmatrix} a_{22} & a_{23} \\ a_{32} & a_{33} \end{pmatrix}$ has $g_2(p, 0) = (p - 1)^3$ choices and a_{11} has $(p - 1)$ choices. Let a_{12} be free to take p choices, after which a_{13} is uniquely determined from $p \mid P_{21}(A)$. This shows that $g(p, 0, 2, 2) = p(p - 1)^4$.

Proof of Part 2. We claim that any matrix belonging to $G(p, 0, 2, 1)$ must be have one of the following forms,

$$\begin{pmatrix} a_{11} & a_{12} & a_{13} \\ 0 & a_{22} & a_{23} \\ 0 & a_{32} & a_{33} \end{pmatrix}, \begin{pmatrix} a_{11} & a_{12} & a_{13} \\ a_{21} & 0 & a_{23} \\ a_{31} & 0 & a_{33} \end{pmatrix} \text{ or } \begin{pmatrix} a_{11} & a_{12} & a_{13} \\ a_{21} & a_{22} & 0 \\ a_{31} & a_{32} & 0 \end{pmatrix}.$$

If a matrix $A \in G(p, 0, 2, 1)$ is in one of the above three forms, then from $p \mid perm(A)$ and $p \nmid \det(A)$, the remaining entries of the second and third row are nonzero (refer to [1]). To begin with, note that if $a_{21} = 0$ then a_{31} must necessarily be 0 as well. For if it was not the case then from $p \mid P_{13}(A)$ we get $a_{22} = 0$. Now from $p \mid P_{11}(A)$ we get either $a_{23} = 0$ or $a_{32} = 0$. The former contradicts invertibility of A while the latter contradicts the congruences:

$$perm(A) \equiv 0 \pmod{p} \text{ and } \det(A) \not\equiv 0 \pmod{p}.$$

So we see that either both a_{21} and a_{31} are 0, or else none of them is. In a similar way we can prove this for (a_{22}, a_{32}) and (a_{23}, a_{33}) . Let $A \in G(p, 0, 2, 1)$. If $a_{21} = 0$ then A is of the first form, and we are done. If not, then $a_{21} \neq 0$ and $a_{31} \neq 0$. Now if $a_{22} = 0$, then A is of the second form, and we are done. Otherwise, $a_{22} \neq 0$ and $a_{32} \neq 0$. Thus all the entries of the submatrix $\begin{pmatrix} a_{21} & a_{22} \\ a_{31} & a_{32} \end{pmatrix}$ are nonzero. Clearly the determinant of this submatrix cannot be zero, otherwise it would contradict the fact that all the entries are nonzero. Now look at a_{23} and a_{33} as variables in the system of congruences:

$$P_{11}(A) = a_{22}a_{33} + a_{23}a_{32} \equiv 0 \pmod{p}, P_{12}(A) = a_{21}a_{33} + a_{23}a_{31} \equiv 0 \pmod{p}.$$

Since $a_{21}a_{32} - a_{22}a_{31} \neq 0$, this system has a unique solution, which is $a_{23} = a_{33} = 0$. Thus, we have shown that every matrix of $G(p, 0, 2, 1)$ must be one of these three forms. We now count each of them. Consider the case when the matrix looks like $\begin{pmatrix} a_{11} & a_{12} & a_{13} \\ 0 & a_{22} & a_{23} \\ 0 & a_{32} & a_{33} \end{pmatrix}$. There are $g_2(p, 0) = (p - 1)^3$ ways to choose the submatrix $\begin{pmatrix} a_{22} & a_{23} \\ a_{32} & a_{33} \end{pmatrix}$ and $(p - 1)$ ways to choose a_{11} . There are p choices for a_{12} . After we choose a_{12} , there will be one choice of a_{13} which will make $P_{21}(A) = 0$, which we do not want. So there are $(p - 1)$ choices for a_{13} . So the total choices become $p(p - 1)^5$.

We now count the possible choices when the matrix looks like $\begin{pmatrix} a_{11} & a_{12} & a_{13} \\ a_{21} & 0 & a_{23} \\ a_{31} & 0 & a_{33} \end{pmatrix}$

or $\begin{pmatrix} a_{11} & a_{12} & a_{13} \\ a_{21} & a_{22} & 0 \\ a_{31} & a_{32} & 0 \end{pmatrix}$. In fact, they both have equal number of choices, as will

be clear after we illustrate how to count one of them. Suppose we are counting the matrices of the form $\begin{pmatrix} a_{11} & a_{12} & a_{13} \\ a_{21} & 0 & a_{23} \\ a_{31} & 0 & a_{33} \end{pmatrix}$. There are $g_2(p, 0) = (p - 1)^3$ ways

to choose the submatrix $\begin{pmatrix} a_{21} & a_{23} \\ a_{31} & a_{33} \end{pmatrix}$ and $(p - 1)$ ways to choose a_{12} . Note how $P_{21}(A) = a_{12}a_{33} + a_{13}a_{32} = a_{12}a_{33}$. So there are p choices each for a_{13} and a_{11} .

Thus the total choices for the second form are $p^2(p-1)^4$. The other form is dealt with in the exact same way. Finally, we arrive at

$$g(p, 0, 2, 1) = p(p-1)^5 + 2p^2(p-1)^4 = p(p-1)^4(3p-1) = (3p-1)g(p, 0, 2, 2).$$

Proof of Part 3. In this case we have $0 = \text{perm}(A) = a_{13}P_{13}(A)$ and $p \nmid P_{13}(A)$ hence $a_{13} = 0$. We also claim that $p \nmid a_{21} \cdot a_{22} \cdot a_{23}$. If $p \mid a_{21}$, then from $p \mid P_{12}(A)$ we get $a_{23} = 0$ or $a_{31} = 0$. If $a_{31} = 0$, then $p \nmid P_{13}(A)$ gives $a_{21} \neq 0$, which is absurd. If $a_{23} = 0$ then $p \mid P_{11}(A)$ gives either $a_{22} = 0$ or $a_{33} = 0$, both of which contradict the invertibility of A . In a similar way we can show that $p \nmid a_{22}a_{23}$. Now once we fix a_{23} which has $(p-1)$ choices, we see that a_{33} is determined as $a_{33} = \frac{-a_{32}a_{23}}{a_{22}} = \frac{-a_{31}a_{23}}{a_{21}}$.

This gives $a_{21}a_{32} - a_{22}a_{31} = 0$. So how many choices are there for $B = \begin{pmatrix} a_{21} & a_{22} \\ a_{31} & a_{32} \end{pmatrix}$?

We claim that none of the a_{31} or a_{32} can be zero. Suppose $a_{31} = 0$. Then from $p \mid P_{12}(A)$, we have either $a_{21} = 0$ or $a_{33} = 0$. Thus if $a_{31} = 0$, then we have $a_{33} = 0$. But then from $a_{33} = 0$, $p \mid P_{11}(A)$ we get that $a_{32} = 0$, so A cannot be invertible. It can be proved in a similar way that $a_{32} \neq 0$. With these observations we are ready to compute $g(p, 0, 1, 3)$.

From $a_{21} \neq 0, a_{22} \neq 0$ the total choices for the first row of B are $(p-1)^2$. The second row of B can only be a nonzero multiple of the first row, thus it has $(p-1)$ choices. Thus the total choices for the matrix B are $(p-1)^3$. Let a_{11} have p choices. Once we fix a_{11} , then it follows from $\det(A) \equiv 0 \pmod{p}$ and $a_{21}a_{33} - a_{23}a_{31} \neq 0$ we have $(p-1)$ choices for a_{12} . Thus, the total choices become $p(p-1)^5 = (p-1)g(p, 0, 2, 2)$.

Proof of Part 4. First observe that it is impossible to have $a_{23} = a_{33} = 0$ because that would contradict $p \nmid P_{12}(A)$. We prove the result in two cases: $p \mid a_{23} \cdot a_{33}$ and $p \nmid a_{23} \cdot a_{33}$.

Let $p \mid a_{33}$. Then from $p \mid P_{11}(A)$, where $P_{11}(A) = a_{22}a_{33} + a_{23}a_{32}$, we have $p \mid a_{32}$. This leaves $g_2(p, 0) = (p-1)^3$ choices for $\begin{pmatrix} a_{12} & a_{13} \\ a_{22} & a_{23} \end{pmatrix}$ and $(p-1)$ choices for a_{31} .

Finally a_{11} and a_{12} are free to take any values, thus the total choices are $p^2(p-1)^4$. We could also have begun with $p \mid a_{23}$. Thus the total number of matrices when $p \mid a_{23} \cdot a_{33}$ are $2p^2(p-1)^4$.

We now suppose that $p \nmid a_{23} \cdot a_{33}$. There are $(p-1)^2$ ways to choose the ordered pair (a_{23}, a_{33}) . In this case it is easy to see that $p \nmid a_{22}a_{32}$. First observe that $p \mid P_{11}(A)$, where $P_{11}(A) = a_{22}a_{33} + a_{23}a_{32}$, so $p \mid a_{22}$ if and only if $p \mid a_{32}$. Hence, if $p \mid a_{22}$, then $\text{perm}(A) = a_{12}P_{12}(A)$ forces $a_{12} = 0$ which contradicts the invertibility of A .

So now a_{22} has $(p-1)$ choices. After fixing a_{22} , a_{32} is uniquely determined from $p \mid P_{11}(A)$. Now let a_{21} be free to take any of the p values. Since $p \nmid P_{12}(A)$, where $P_{12}(A) = a_{21}a_{33} + a_{23}a_{31}$, there is a unique value of a_{31} which will render $P_{12}(A) = 0$. We throw out that value, so we are left with $(p-1)$ choices for

a_{31} . Now all that is left is to choose the first row. Let a_{13} be free to take p values. Then a_{12} is uniquely determined because of the relation $\text{perm}(A) = a_{12}P_{12}(A) + a_{13}P_{13}(A)$. Finally we need to choose a_{11} . We claim first that $(a_{22}a_{33} - a_{23}a_{32}) \neq 0$. Otherwise we would end up with multiple zeroes in $\begin{pmatrix} a_{22} & a_{23} \\ a_{32} & a_{33} \end{pmatrix}$ which is absurd since in this case all the four entries are nonzero. Therefore we are left with $(p - 1)$ values of a_{11} because we will throw one value out which will make the determinant of A zero. The total choices in this case are $p^2(p - 1)^5$. Thus,

$$g(p, 0, 1, 2) = 2p^2(p - 1)^4 + p^2(p - 1)^5 = p^2(p - 1)^4(p + 1) = p(p + 1)g(p, 0, 2, 2).$$

Proof of Part 5. It is easy to see that

$$g(p, 0, 1, 1) = g(p, 0) - g(p, 0, 1, 2) - g(p, 0, 1, 3) - g(p, 0, 2, 1) - g(p, 0, 2, 2).$$

□

We now compute $g(p, 0, 1, 1)$ independently. With that we have an alternate proof for Theorem 3.

4.6. Independent Proof of Part 5 of Theorem 5

Let $A = [a_{ij}] \in G(p, 0, 1, 1)$. Then we have $p \nmid P_{11}(A)$. Let $D_{11} = \det(B)$, where $B = \begin{pmatrix} a_{22} & a_{23} \\ a_{32} & a_{33} \end{pmatrix}$. Two possibilities arise, $D_{11} = 0$ and $D_{11} \neq 0$.

4.6.1. When $D_{11} = 0$.

First note that none of the entries of B is zero. For example, if $a_{22} = 0$ then we have either $a_{23} = 0$ or $a_{32} = 0$. But that forces $p \mid P_{11}(A)$. Hence the matrix B can be chosen $(p - 1)^3$ ways, as (a_{22}, a_{23}) can be chosen in $(p - 1)^2$ ways. Then we are left with $(p - 1)$ choices for second row of B . Let a_{13}, a_{31} be free to choose any values, then it is easy to see that each of a_{12}, a_{21} can take $p - 1$ values. Thus total number of matrices in $G(p, 0, 1, 1)$ with $D_{11} = 0$ are $p^2(p - 1)^5$.

4.6.2. When $D_{11} \neq 0$.

First of all note that we cannot have $(a_{21}, a_{31}) = (0, 0)$ for this would contradict either the invertibility of A if $a_{11} = 0$ or $\text{perm}(A) = 0$ if $a_{11} \neq 0$ as $p \nmid P_{11}(A)$. Table 3 illustrates how the rest of the proof follows. The value of $g(p, 0, 1, 1)$ as stated in Theorem 5 can now be obtained after

$$p^2(p - 1)^5 + 2p(p - 1)^4(p^2 + 1) + 2p^2(p - 1)^5 + 2p(p - 1)^6 + \dots .$$

Case 1: When $a_{21} = 0$ or $a_{31} = 0$. Let $a_{21} = 0$. Then a_{31} has $(p - 1)$ choices. From [1] we have $g_2(p, 1) = (p - 1)(p^2 + 1)$. Consequently, the total choices for B

Condition	Subconditions	Number of matrices
$p \mid a_{21}a_{31}$		$2p(p-1)^4(p^2+1)$
$p \nmid a_{21}a_{31}$	Exactly one of $a_{22} = 0$ or $a_{32} = 0$ $p \nmid a_{22}a_{32}$ but exactly one of a_{23} or a_{33} is zero All the entries of 2nd and 3rd row are nonzero	$2p^2(p-1)^5$ $2p(p-1)^6$ **
** =	$\begin{cases} p(p-1)^4[(p-1)^3 - 2(p-1)^2] & \text{if } p-3 \text{ is not a quadratic residue modulo } p, \\ p(p-1)^4[(p-1)^3 - 2(p-1)^2 - 2(p-1)] & \text{if } p-3 \text{ is a quadratic residue modulo } p. \end{cases}$	

Table 3: $D_{11} \neq 0$.

are $(p-1)^2(p^2+1)$. Let a_{12} and a_{13} each be free to take p values. Each time we do this, we get a unique value for a_{11} from $perm(A) = 0$. So there seem to be p^2 possible ordered triads (a_{11}, a_{12}, a_{13}) . However we must remove p of them because those will cause the determinant to become 0. Thus the first row has $p^2 - p$ choices. So in this case, the total choices are $2p(p-1)^4(p^2+1)$.

Case 2: When $a_{21} \neq 0$ and $a_{31} \neq 0$ but exactly one of $a_{22} = 0$ or $a_{32} = 0$. Suppose $a_{22} = 0$. Then a_{33} can take p values and $p \nmid a_{23}a_{32}$ as $P_{11}(A) \neq 0$. So there are a total of $p(p-1)^2$ choices for the submatrix B . There are $(p-1)^2$ choices for (a_{21}, a_{31}) . Finally as discussed earlier, there are $p(p-1)$ choices for the first row. Thus, the total choices are $2p^2(p-1)^5$.

Case 3: When $a_{21} \neq 0, a_{31} \neq 0, a_{22} \neq 0$ and $a_{32} \neq 0$ but exactly one of a_{23} or $a_{33} = 0$. If $a_{23} = 0$, then we have $(p-1)^5$ choices for the second and third row combined. The first row can be chosen in $p(p-1)$ ways. But we could also start with $a_{33} = 0$, making the total choices for this case $2p(p-1)^6$.

Case 4: All the entries in the 2nd and 3rd rows are nonzero. There are $(p-1)^3$ choices for the third row. It is easy to see that there are $[(p-1)^3 - 2(p-1)^2]$ choices for the second row, when $(p-3)$ is not a quadratic residue of p . This is because we have two more constraints, namely that $P_{11}(A) \neq 0$ and $D_{11} \neq 0$. So every time we fix a_{21} and a_{22} , we will get one value of a_{23} that will make $P_{11}(A) = 0$ and one value will make $D_{11} = 0$. Now after fixing the third row, we imitate the proof of the part related to the role of quadratic residues in Theorem 3. So we subtract another $2(p-1)$ from the total choices of the second row whenever $(p-3)$ is a quadratic residue of p . Again, after fixing the second and third row, the first row can be chosen in $p(p-1)$ ways.

Now from the discussion provided in Section 3 we can compute $g(p^k, 0, i, j)$ from the identity $g(p^k, 0, i, j) = p^{8(k-1)}g(p, 0, i, j)$. But note that $g(n, 0, i, j)$ is not multiplicative in n . Hence, finding the value of $g(n, 0, i, j)$ is an interesting problem.

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